

Comparison of water and microwave blanching of mangoes and sensory evaluation

Key words :

Blanching, mangoes, microwaves, water bath,
sensory analysis

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Abstract

Mangos are fruits with high valuable nutritional properties. However, like all fruits, they are perishable and have a really short shelf-life. Moreover, they are seasonal and therefore not available all year long in our shops. This is the main reason why processes are developed to extend their shelf-life. One in particular is blanching. Prior step to many preservation processes of fruits and vegetables, blanching is traditionally done by immersing the fruits in boiling water for a few minutes. However new methods which are faster and more sustainable are starting to raise and to be studied, like for example microwave blanching. In this study, we tried to determine the optimum parameters of mango blanching with microwaves and to compare it with similar conditions with conventional water blanching. We wanted also to evaluate the enzyme inactivation in both cases. However, these measurements couldn't be performed during my internship period due to technical difficulties and limited time. We did a sensorial analysis to know if consumers could perceive a difference between the two blanching types. The results acquired showed that there was no significant difference in the sensory attributes between the two blanching methods of mangoes.

Keywords: blanching, mangoes, microwaves, water bath, sensory analysis

Résumé

Les mangues sont des fruits aux propriétés nutritionnelles très intéressantes. Cependant, comme tous fruits et légumes, ils sont périssables et leur durée de vie relativement courte. De plus, leurs conditions de croissance les rendent particulièrement difficile à avoir toute l'année. C'est pourquoi des procédés sont développés afin d'allonger cette durée de vie. Un en particulier est le blanchiment. Etape de prétraitement des principales méthodes de conservation des fruits et légumes, elle est traditionnellement réalisée en immergeant les fruits dans de l'eau bouillante pendant un certain temps. Cependant des nouvelles méthodes plus écologiques et rapides commencent à être développées et recherchées comme notamment le blanchiment aux micro-ondes. Dans ce travail nous avons cherché à déterminer les paramètres optimaux de blanchiment des mangues aux micro-ondes et les comparer avec des conditions similaires de blanchiment traditionnel. Nous voulions mesurer ensuite l'inactivation des enzymes dans les deux cas pour déterminer la méthode la plus efficace. Cette étape n'a malheureusement pas pu être réalisée durant ma période de stage à cause de problème matériel. Nous avons également fait une analyse sensorielle pour savoir si les consommateurs perçoivent une différence sur les mangues blanchies selon les deux méthodes. Les résultats des tests semblent montrer qu'il n'y aurait pas différence significative entre les échantillons.

Mots-clefs : blanchiment, mangues, micro-ondes, bain marie, analyse sensorielle

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I. Introduction

Foods are highly perishable matrices due to their interaction with the environment. For example apples left in ambient conditions for a few minutes will become dark because of oxidation reactions. Heat, air and light, are factors accelerating the biological and biochemical reactions occurring in the food. Those reactions affect not only the sensorial properties but also the nutritional qualities and the safety of the food (Guiamba, 2016). Food preservation refers to all the technologies and procedures used to prevent food from any kind of spoilage. Those can be physical, biological, microbiological, chemical and biochemical. The main target of food preservation methods is to extend what we call the shelf-life of a food product. The shelf-life is defined as the maximum duration of storage where the food quality is retained and that the product remains safe. When the quality or a sensory attribute is damaged, the food is becoming unsuitable for consumption and we reach the end of the shelf-life. The table 1 (Rahman, 2007) is showing some examples of quality losses that food preservation methods are fighting against.

Table 1 : Exemple of the major food quality losses (Rahman, 2007)

Major Quality-Loss Mechanisms				
Microbiological	Enzymatic	Chemical	Physical	Mechanical
Microorganism growth	Browning	Color loss	Collapse	Bruising due to vibration
Off-flavor	Color change	Flavor loss	Controlled release	Cracking
Toxin production	Off-flavor	Nonenzymatic browning	Crystallization	Damage due to pressure
		Nutrient loss	Flavor encapsulation	
		Oxidation–reduction	Phase changes	
		Rancidity	Recrystallization	
			Shrinkage	
			Transport of component	

In a world, where consumers are having less time to go to the grocery store and less time for cooking, long lasting food is a help. This is also another reason why it has become a major goal of the food factories. Several kind of techniques and processes are used nowadays to make food last longer. A crucial point is that all of those processes should retain the quality, ensure the safety, be sustainable and cost efficient.

Due to the subject of the work, we are going to focus mainly on the methods used for fruits preservation.

There are different approaches of food preservation processes according to the mode of action. Most of the methods are based on the inactivation of bacteria or enzymes by heating or using a high pressure, but it can also be done through the use of chemicals, the control of the atmosphere and the control of the water (Rahman, 2007). The choice of the preservation method depends on the food characteristics and its origin. The 3 main methods used nowadays for fruits are being described below:

- Canning: is based on heating at high temperatures (from 100°C to 130 °C) some food put previously in jars. This destroys all possible pathogens (Rahman, 2007).
- Drying: one of the oldest methods of food preservation (sun drying) based on the control of water. It reduces the water activity by exposing the food to heated air to remove its moisture without cooking it. Therefore, microbial growth is avoided. This method however is changing a lot the sensory properties of the product such as the flavor, the aroma, and the texture, but it is the most cost efficient method (Rahman, 2007).
- Freezing: this method is based on the physical transformation of liquid water into ice by reducing the temperature below the freezing point (commonly - 18°C). Such a temperature stops the microbial activity and slows down the enzymatic reactions. Therefore the organoleptic properties of the food are changing only really slowly during the storage. This method is preferred against the others because it retains better the quality (Rahman, 2007).

All those three methods are however requiring a prior step: blanching.

Blanching is a pre-treatment prior to many preservation methods applied to fruits and vegetables that enables to prolong their shelf-life. In fact, it inactivates the major enzymes responsible of the natural deterioration of the fruit, by mild heating, at a certain temperature, and for a limited time therefore denaturizing them (Ramesh *et al.*, 2002).

A vitamin which is significantly affected by the losses is the ascorbic acid. It is in fact a very sensitive vitamin which can be easily oxidized by the enzyme ascorbic acid oxidase (AAO). However, it cannot be produced by the body hence the importance to have a diet with enough sources of supply. Since it is mainly contained in fruits and vegetables, industrial processes have to be optimized to keep their nutritional quality. Another enzyme is the pectin methyl esterase (PME), which affects the pectin and therefore the texture of the fruit on one hand. On the other hand PME hydrolyses the pectin, releasing methanol, a toxic substance for humans (Gonzalez *et al.*, 2011).

Blanching is used a lot in the freezing industry as a pre-treatment to help preserving the color, the texture and the nutritional quality of the product. However thermal processes can change the sensorial properties and the nutritional value (Patricia *et al.*, 2011).

The most common methods that we use are called conventional blanching (figure 1a). It is mainly the traditional way which means, water blanching (immersion of the food in a hot water bath) and also steam blanching. Time and temperature are critical parameters during blanching because too high temperatures or extended time period of treatment could cause undesirable characteristics and damages on the food matrix. (Rahman, 2007).

Blanching can be done at high temperatures, between 80°C and 100°C, but for a short time (HTST), but also at low temperatures for a long time (LTLT) which has been proposed in order to improve the texture quality and retention of some nutrients. Therefore, the LTLT temperature is in a range between 50°C and 70°C (Rahman, 2007).

Figure 1: Most common (a ; on the left) conventional and (b ; on the right) non conventional blanching methods.

Conventional blanching methods are mastered and well adapted to the industries nowadays, but they are not sustainable due to the high water wastes and energy consumption. This is the reason why new blanching ways, or as we call them, non-conventional methods (figure 1b), have been studied a lot recently (Xin *et al.*, 2015). Among those, the major ones are the microwave and infrared blanching.

Microwave blanching is really interesting from several points of view. Studies have shown that at an industrial scale, the energy consumption and cost of production are divided by two between water blanching and microwave blanching (Patricia *et al.*, 2011). In fact, it produces much less water waste and the heating treatment is faster. Moreover, nutrients are better retained inside of the food since they cannot diffuse (Muftugil, 1986). So we get in the end a product with a high nutritional quality. For all those reasons, microwave blanching seems to be the ideal method. Why is it not used everywhere then? There is one major problem: the heat repartition inside of the food is not fully homogeneous (Boyes *et al.*, 1997; Vadivambal & Javas, 2010). This temperature difference is bringing a problem in the homogeneity of the enzyme inactivation. Moreover, the cost of changing the whole equipment in an industry is quite high and profitable only on the long term.

Microwave heating is depending on several factors. First of all and the most important one is the moisture content since it is directly affecting the dielectric properties of

the food and as a consequence, the absorbed power (Rahman, 2007). The food, which is highly composed of water, is sensitive to microwave heating. In fact, the H₂O molecule is dipolar and changing its orientation according to the magnetic field vector. Then, the mass which has also a link with the amount of absorbed power has a huge influence. The initial temperature of the food, the shape of the food and the location in the microwave affect the depth penetration of the microwaves (Ramesh, 2002).

Mangoes (*Mangifera indica L.*) are the second most trade tropical fruits over the world after bananas. Originated from Asia 4000 years ago, the mango trees has a robust shape that enables to grow and carry fruits such as mangoes that can have a seed weighting from 50g to 2 kilos depending on the varieties. The mango tree needs specific conditions to grow. In fact it is used to intensive rain periods followed by a dry season generating a stress that provokes the blossoming (Nadie *et al.*, 2009). This is the reason why they are mainly produced in the tropical climates countries. The production hasn't stopped increasing since the past years and therefore raised from 29,6 million tons in 2006 to 34,4 million tons in 2010 and is dominated by Asia (figure 2). Figure 3 is showing the repartition of the production within Asia in 2010 (ECOWAS, 2011).

Figure 2: Graphic of the repartition of the world production of mangoes in 2010 (in percentage %) (ECOWAS, 2011)

Figure 3: Graphic of the repartition of the production of mangoes in Asia in 2010 (in percentage %) (ECOWAS, 2011)

Its composition and richness makes it a particularly interesting fruit from a nutritional point of view. The fruit is divided into three parts: the skin, the pulp and the seed. Each of them carries some specific characteristics. The pulp is the main consumed part of the mango. It can be eaten raw or processed into various products according to the ripening stage. Young mangos are usually used for dehydrated products and chutneys whereas ripped mangos are used to freeze, can, make juices and nectars puree. This part is largely appreciated thanks

to its taste but also its high nutritional value. In fact, it is well-balanced in minerals and vitamins (table 2) (Masibo & He, 2009).

Table 2: Composition of a 100g of riped mango (Masibo and He, 2009)

Composition for 100 g of ripe mango	Amount	Composition for 100 g of ripe mango	Amount
Calories	62.1-63.7 kcal	Phosphorus	5.5-17.9 mg
Water	78.9-82.8g	Iron	0.20-0.63 mg
Protein	0.36-0.40g	Carotene	0.135-1.872 mg
Fat	0.30-0.53g	Ascorbic acid	7.8-172 mg
Carbohydrates	16.20 – 17.18 g	Tryptophan	3-6 mg
Fiber	0.85-1.06 g	Lysine	32-37 mg
calcium	6.1-12.8 mg	Methionine	4 mg

Mangoes are excellent sources of fibers. Moreover, they contain many bioactive compounds such as polyphenols, mainly quercetin, and carotenoids which are good antioxidants providing heart health benefits (Masibo & He, 2009).

The peel and the seed are nowadays wastes of the mango processing. However, they are major by-products thanks to their composition. They could be used in food formulation to provide health benefits (Masibo & He, 2009).

There are over 1000 varieties of mangoes but only a few of them are commercialized. Among those we can find the Kent variety which is one of the most common and that we used during our study. The Kent variety appeared in Guinea in 1949 and is characterized by a low water content 79.53%, and a sugar content of 22 brix degrees, hence its good shelf-life. It is general sweet compared to some other variety. Their color changes from green to yellow and red along the ripening process, making them really attractive. Kent variety mangoes match well with the European standards hence its success (Rey *et al.*, 2004).

Microwave blanched mangoes could be an alternative to water blanched mangoes saving therefore not only energy but also time and the nutritional quality of the fruit. The aim of this study was to define the optimum parameters to blanch mangoes in the microwave and compare it to water blanching. We also investigated with a sensory analysis if this novel proposed process was creating a new product by changing the final characteristics or not, that, in this case, would be liked by the consumers.

II. Materials and methods

A. Materials

1. Mangoes

The mangoes were provided from a local store in Gothenburg and only from the Kent variety at a medium stage of maturity.

2. Samples

In order to have a standard shape and size, the samples were cut by means of a sample holder made of polyester (figure 4) with a diameter of 2.5 cm. 4 little holes had been made on one side, to insert and stabilize the optical fibers in order to follow the temperature at different positions inside of the fruit during the heating process.

Figure 4 : A mango sample and the sample holder and

3. Blanching equipment

a. Water blanching

The equipment used for the water blanching was a typical water bath. Some water was poured in a metallic pot and placed on a heating plate equipped of a regulation of the temperature and a magnetic stirring. 200 mL of water was used for one sample of mango to be sure that the fruit would be fully immersed. The pot was closed by an aluminum paper to avoid light. As we wanted to have consistency in temperature measurements in all experiments, optical fibers have been used to follow the temperature of the mango at different positions because metal thermocouples are not appropriate for measuring the temperature in microwave application. A tea infuser was used to stabilize the optical fiber inside of the fruit in the case of water blanching. Optical fibers were connected with a logger station which through Q OptiLink software installed on a PC, could record the data.

b. Microwave blanching

The microwave heating equipment (figure 5) consisted of a magnetron, an isolator (National 2722 162 11171), an auto tuner (Homer STHT V1.5), a three-stub and finally one piece of waveguide with a single stub that connected everything to the modified domestic microwave oven. The equipment can be seen in figure 8. The three-stub and the single stub together enabled to customize matching (i.e. reflection of microwave power) between the load and the rest of the system. The isolator isolates the magnetron from the system thanks to a water load. The auto tuner is in this setup only used for its ability to measure forward and reflected power, while the role of the microwave switch is to enable removal of the initial full power peak that starts every new cycle of microwave power

generation (necessary for the power supply to start up the magnetron). Generated microwave power is computer-controlled by customized software in the approximate range of 50 to 1100 W.

Figure 5 : The modified microwave oven used for blanching

B. Methods

1. Characteristics of the mangoes

a. Dry matter

To measure the water content of the mangoes, we have calculated first the dry matter. 4 samples were placed in a drying vacuum oven for 24 hours at about 70°C. The initial weight of the samples, the weight of the plate, and the gross weight after drying were measured to be able to calculate the percentage of dry matter by the following way (1):

$$\% \text{ dry matter} = \frac{\text{weight of the dried sample}}{\text{initial weight}} * 100 \quad (1)$$

a. Water content

With the four repetitions, we have then calculated the average percentage of the water content the following way (2):

$$\text{Water content} = 100 - \% \text{ dry matter} \quad (2)$$

b. Brix number

The measurements of the brix number have been made with an automatic refractometer, Refracto 30PX and mango purée. Two samples have been cut from both sides, (green and red), to compare and evaluate if there was a variation between them.

2. Blanching of the mangoes

a. General protocol

After purchase, the mangoes were stored for limited time in the refrigerator (maximum 4 days) at about 4°C. The samples were taken on the both parts of the mangoes around the seed in the appropriate way to get 4 samples from one mango. The samples were cut just before each experiment, to preserve as much as possible the vitamin C contents. Between each assay, the mango was wrapped into aluminum foil and placed back in the refrigerator to limit the oxidation reactions. Each sample was weighted after being cut to be able to link later the enzyme inactivation to the weight. Optical fibers were inserted in the sample according to the different experiments.

Once the sample was ready, it was blanched in the microwave or in the water according to the different conditions.

After blanching, the samples were immersed into an ice water bath (0°C) for 5 minutes to stop the inactivation process. The cold bath was also covered to limit the vitamin C degradation by light exposure. They were then quickly frozen with liquid nitrogen and stored tubes previously filled with nitrogen to remove all the air, and wrapped with dark paper at -80°C. Figure 6 shows the succession of steps of the main protocol.

Figure 6 : Steps of the blanching experimental protocol

b. Microwave blanching conditions

The samples were placed with the sample holder in the middle of the modified microwave oven cavity. The parameters were set according to the following conditions. For the HTST, the experiment was stopped once the central temperature of the sample reached 92°C (the time needed depends on the sample).

Table 1: Microwave HTHT blanching conditions

	High temperature short time (HTST)		
Power set (W)	144	186	224
Aim	92 °C in the middle of the sample		

For the LTLT microwave blanching, a first power was set until reaching the aim temperature of 70 °C in the middle of the sample. Then the temperature was stabilized at a lower power with pulses (table 4).

Table 2: Microwave LTLT blanching conditions

	Low temperature long time (LTLT)		
First power set (W)	140	190	280
Aim	70 °C in the middle of the sample		
Stabilized power (W)	140		
Total running time (min)	10		

c. Water blanching conditions

Once ready, the samples were immersed into the water bath set with different temperature conditions (table 5). The experiment was stopped when the middle temperature of the sample reached 92°C.

Table 3: Water HTST blanching conditions

	High temperature short time (HTST)		
Running time (min)	1	2	3
Water temperature (°C)	92		

For the LTLT water blanching, the water bath was set to a first temperature (table 6). Once the sample inside, the set temperature was changed to 70°C and the experiments was stopped after 10 minutes.

Table 4: Water LTLT blanching conditions

	Low temperature long time (LTLT)		
First temperature set (°C)	55	65	70
Stabilized temperature (°C)	70		
Total running time (min)	10		

3. Absorbed power

To understand better the equipment and confirm the values given by the auto turner about the power absorbed by the sample, we have made an additional experiment. We have made a mango puree that we weighted and put inside of the sample holder, closed on one side by a tape, and blanched it as for the other samples. We have measured the temperature before and after heating after a quick homogenization to calculate the

temperature difference. The experiment has been repeated for 3 different times: 40, 80 and 120 seconds.

4. Sensory tests

For the both tests that have been performed, the mangoes were stored in a fridge at 4 degrees until being cut and blanched for a short or long time in the microwave or the water. The following conditions (table 7) have been chosen for blanching the mangoes for the sensory tests since we couldn't use the optical fibers and damage the structure of the samples.

Table 5: Microwave and water blanching conditions for the sensory tests

	Microwave		Water	
	HTST	LTLT	HTST	LTLT
Power (W) / water temperature (°C)	186	140	92	70
Time (s)	135	600	135	600

They were then placed in the little plastic cups and stored in the freezer at -20 degrees for 5 days. The night before the test, we placed them in the fridge to defreeze and they were taken out 30 min before each degustation to be able to reach a temperature of around 17,5 °C in the heart of the sample.

The samples have been named with three digit codes and with an order of presentation following a "carré Latin" to lower the effect of the position (Figure 1 of the annexes). The testers had some water available to rinse and neutralize the taste in their mouth. The tests have been performed in a little room which was calm (figure 2 in the annexes). We carefully chose the samples in order to ensure that each evaluator of the panel tested samples coming from the same mango due to the natural variation of the ripeness of the fruit.

a. Triangle tests

The panel was composed of 18 non trained persons. The people were asked to find out the odd sample among three samples of mango knowing that two were identical and one different (figure 3 of the annexes).

Each consumer received for the triangle tests the 6 samples settled in two separate lines and some oral and written instructions. The mangoes were cut into two pieces to enable the consumer to try again.

b. Description test

The panel consisted in 22 people divided as 54,54% of women and 45,45% of men. (The test had been prepared for 24 persons but 2 people didn't fill the questions as we needed). One

person among the 22 didn't like mangoes. The frequency of consumption was divided as followed:

- at least once a week : 4.54%
- at least once a month : 31.81%
- once each 6 months : 45.45%
- once a year or less : 13.63%
- never : 4.54%

The questions asked were about their preferences regarding the color, smell, texture, taste and their acceptance for those same attributes for each of the four samples. Finally the general appreciation was asked (figure 4 and 5 of the annexes). The answers were reported on a 9 point scale for the preferences and a "just about right" scale for the acceptance. This last scale enables to determine the ideal sample.

This kind of tests require trained people and a huge panel, (at least 60 persons), but it was not possible to reach this number of people under the present study.

III. Results and discussion

To compare water and microwave blanching of mangoes, firstly, experiments on the mangoes characteristics (water, content, brix degree) have been made. Then, three different approaches for HTST and LTLT microwave and water blanching were carried out. Two sensory tests have been performed in order to investigate the influence of the different blanching methods on the organoleptic characteristics.

A. Characteristics of the mangoes

The following table shows the results acquired regarding the dry matter and water content.

Table 6: Results of the dry matter and water content experiments with 4 samples of a Kent mango

Repetitions	Plate (g)	Plate +sample (g)	Initial sample mass (g)	Dried sample mass (g)	% dry matter	% Water content
1	0.437	9.508	9.071	1.391	15.33%	84.67
2	0.436	9.396	8.960	1.314	14.66%	85.34%
3	0.436	9.270	8.834	1.003	11.35%	88.65
4	0.436	9.592	9.156	1.599	17.46%	82.54
average	0.436	9.441	9.005	1.327	14.71%	85.29%

The average water content obtained with the four samples is higher than the one from the literature 79.53 % (Rey *et al.*, 2004). This most probably comes from the origin and the maturity degree of the fruit.

The coming table is now presenting the results of the brix measurements.

Table 7: Brix values from both side of a Kent mango

Repetition	Green side	Red side
1	14.5	15.1
2	14.5	15.2
Average	14.5	15.15

The brix value is this time lower than the one from the literature (22 brix degree (Rey *et al.*, 2004)). There are many possible explanation again, the main one being maybe the origin of the fruit and the ripeness stage. In any case, it is interesting to notice the difference between the side of the mango : the red side which is the one growing face to the sun is a little bit sweeter than the green side.

We can already see the numerous sources of possible variation between the mangoes : the size, the maturity, the water content, the brix value. This makes the work with fruit hard for the high repeatability of the experiments. For this reason, several repetitions are needed in each experiment when fruits are the selected food matrices.

B. Blanching treatments

1. Temperatures in the mango sample

The following graphics show the representative temperature profiles at four different positions (figure 6) inside of the mango and at two different powers during microwave blanching (figure 7 and 8).

Figure 6 : schematic representation of a mango sample and the position of the optical fibers

Figure 7 :Temperatures in the middle of a mango sample at 4 different heights at 144W (in green position 1, in orange position 2, in yellow position 3, in pink position 4)

We can see easily on those two graphics the temperature differences inside of the sample between the different positions. At the two different powers, the gap between the coldest and the warmest position is about 30°C, which is quite important. This illustrates the problem that we mentioned in the introduction and that is represented on the model figure 9 about the uneven microwave heating distribution.

Figure 8 : Temperatures in the middle of a mango sample at 4 different heights at 224W (in green position 1, in orange position 2, in yellow position 3, in pink position 4)

Figure 9 : Model of the temperature repartition inside of the mango cylinder right after microwave blanching. The white part is the warmest and the red the coldest.

Another point that can be mentioned is that the position 2 is always the warmest. Indeed, microwave start to heat from the middle but there are also heat losses due to the conduction between the sample and the surface of the cavity. Finally, we can notice on those graphics, the power-time differences: at 224 W it takes about 60 seconds to reach 80°C whereas it requires about the double time (125 seconds) at 144 W emitted power.

2. HTST and LTLT blanching treatments

The two coming graphics (figure 10 and 11) show the HTST representative curves of the temperature profiles during microwave and water blanching.

Figure 10 : Representative curves of the central temperature of the mango samples during HTST water blanching (in green 1 min, in orange 2 min, in yellow 3 min)

Figure 11 : Representative curves of the central temperature of the mango samples during HTST microwave blanching ((in green 144 W, in orange 186 W, in yellow 224 W)

The graphics showed a big difference about the temperature inside of the mango between the two blanching methods. In fact, the geometric center of the sample only reached 70°C after 3 minutes of water blanching whereas in the microwave at 224 W it reached 70°C within 45 seconds, and 90°C, which was our aim, within 65 seconds. We can suppose that this difference has an impact on the inactivation of the enzymes. The mango sample in the water bath would have reached 92°C as well but after a longer time in those same conditions. This can be explained by the different heat transmission. In a water bath, the heat is transmitted from the water to the mango by convection. The quantity of heat (3) exchanged between the solid and the liquid is depending on the temperature differences, the surface of exchange, the heat capacity of the liquid and its speed.

$$\frac{\delta Q}{dt} = h * \Delta T * dS \quad (3)$$

Where $\frac{\delta Q}{dt}$ is the transmitted power in W, h the convection coefficient in W/m².K, ΔT the temperature difference between the solid and the liquid in K and dS the exchange surface in m² (Bargach, 2006).

In the case of the microwave, the heat transfer comes from the agitation of the water molecules which is immediately influenced by the magnetic field, hence the speed of heating.

The water blanching settings chosen were chosen with respect to the same time periods of blanching. It could be also interesting to check the time needed to reach the aim temperature.

Those two last graphics (figure 12 and 13) show the LTLT representative curves of the temperature profiles during microwave and water blanching.

Figure 12 : Representative curves of the central temperature of the mango samples during LTLT water blanching (in green from 55 to 70°C, in orange from 65 to 70°C, in yellow 70°C)

Figure 13 : Representative curves of the central temperature of the mango samples during LTLT microwave blanching (in green 140 W, in orange 190 W, in yellow 280 W)

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Those results show clearly that in the case of microwave blanching the maximum temperature is reached much faster than in water blanching. In fact, it takes between 50 and 100 seconds to reach 70°C according to the different power whereas it takes about 400 seconds with the warmest water bath to get to the same temperature. As a consequence, microwave blanching can be assumed to use less energy and to be more sustainable if the enzymatic inactivation result is comparable. Moreover, reaching a high temperature faster means that for a same blanching duration, the sample in the microwave is staying at the inactivation temperature for longer, which can possibly give better results on the enzyme inactivation.

C. Absorbed power

To calculate the absorbed power for each time duration, we used the equation (4) where $C_p \text{ mango} = 3.8 \text{ J/kg/K}$, ΔT in K or °C, the mass in kg and the time in s:

$$Pa = \frac{C_p \text{ mango} * \Delta T * mass}{time} \quad (4)$$

Where ΔT is the average temperature difference since the time 0. For the two last durations we could calculate the absorbed power, Pa_{latest} , inside of each interval with the following equation (5) where $C_p \text{ mango} = 3.8 \text{ J/kg/K}$, ΔT in K or °C, the mass in kg and the time in seconds :

$$Pa_{\text{latest}} = \frac{C_p \text{ mango} * (\Delta T2 - \Delta T1) * mass}{time 2 - time 1} \quad (5)$$

For example, the data obtained for the three different times at 160 W are as followed:

Table 8: Results of the mango purée temperatures after heating

Heating time (s)	Mass of the sample (g)	ΔT (°C)	Average ΔT (°C)	Standard deviation
40	9.4	26.3	22.2	3.8
40	9.4	21.7		
40	9.2	18.7		
80	9.3	23.7	43,6	12.3
80	9.7	53.3		
80	9.4	49.5		
80	9.8	51.9		
80	9.5	39.8		
120	9.5	58.5	56.2	11.4
120	9.7	58.6		
120	9.7	40.2		
120	9.6	67.4		

Then we could calculate the average power absorbed $P_{a_{mean}}$ with the equation 4, from the time 0 until the time step concerned. We also calculated $P_{a_{latest}}$ which is the power absorbed inside of the time duration. Those results are shown in the table 11.

Table 9: Results of the absorbed power calculation

Time (s)	Average ΔT ($^{\circ}C$)	$P_{a_{mean}}$ (W)	$P_{a_{latest}}$ (W)
40	20.1	20.7	20.07
80	43.6	19.7	19.3
120	56.2	16.9	11.3

The figure 14 is divided into the three different time durations and represents the absorbed power from each duration ($P_{a_{latest}}$). It shows that the absorbed power is decreasing over time especially from 80 to 120 seconds. This explains the fast increase of the temperature of the middle of the sample at the beginning of the microwave blanching. We suppose that during the heating process the sample is losing water by evaporation.

Figure 14 : Absorbed power in function of each time duration

The agitation of the water molecules would be less important and this is reflected by the diminution of the absorption of power.

D. Sensory evaluation

Before interpreting the results of the sensory evaluation, we have to keep in mind that those experiments have been made in the frame of our internship, and therefore, the time was restricted. As a consequence, the samples have been stored in the freezer only for 5 days, whereas, to be able to see the influence of the storage, they should stay for at least 3 months. Those results are thus showing the immediate influence of the blanching methods.

1. Triangle tests

The results of those two triangle tests have been analyzed simultaneously. We have set the hypothesis H_0 that the microwave blanched and water blanched mangoes were different. We have inserted the results in the table 12 for both tests. Firstly is the answer given by the participants, and then a code according to if this answer was correct or not.

Table 10: Raw results of the two triangle tests

participant	TRIANGULAR TEST 1		TRIANGULAR TEST 2	
	Answer given	0=incorrect / 1=correct	Answer given	0=incorrect / 1=correct
1	994	0	702	0
2	994	0	9	1
3	994	0	395	0
4	165	0	601	0
5	547	0	601	0
6	165	0	601	0
7	165	1	702	0
8	165	1	702	0
9	994	0	702	0
10	165	0	9	0
11	994	1	9	0
12	165	0	601	0
13	994	0	9	1
14	547	1	395	0
15	994	0	9	1
16	547	0	601	0
17	253	1	601	0
18	253	1	395	1
Total of correct answers		6		4

The critical number of correct answers needed (figure 6 in the annexes) at a risk of 5% is 10. To conclude to a difference between the products, and keep H_0 , the number of correct answer has to be higher than the critical number from the table. For our both triangle tests, the number of correct answers is lower than 10, which means that we reject H_0 and can't conclude that the products are different.

We were expecting the products to taste differently, this is the reason why we had planned afterwards a preference test. According to the results it would have been more judicious to do another triangle test turned in the direction to show if the products were the same.

2. Preference test

A preference test is usually used when we already showed before that the products were different. It enables to know the preferences of the consumers and to choose the best product. In our case, the triangle tests couldn't conclude to a difference, but we still chose to perform the preference test and investigate if there were particular differences. The answers on the scales have been transformed as grades for analysis, as in the following table:

Table 11: Coonnections bewteen the scales and the grade for the statistical Fiedman test

Just about right scale	9 point scale	Grade
Extremely light, weak, though	Dislike extremely	1
Very much light, weak, though	Dislike very much	2
Moderately light, weak, though	Dislike moderately	3
Slightly light, weak, though	Dislike slightly	4
Just about right	Neither like nor dislike	5
Slightly dark, intense, strong	Like slightly	6
Moderately dark, intense, strong	Like moderately	7
Very much dark, intense, strong	Like very much	8
Extremely dark, intense, strong	Like extremely	9

a. Results of the 9 points scale question

We have calculated the average of the grade of the 22 participants for each question in the table 14. The averages have been rounded up to the next or previous tenth.

Table 12: Average of the grades of the results of the Friedman test

Average of the grades					
	attribute	Microwave HTST	Microwave LTLT	Water HTST	Water LTLT
Characteristics	Color	4	4.1	3.8	4.2
	Smell	3.8	4.6	3.8	4.1
	Softness	4.9	4.6	4.5	4.7
	sweetness	4.2	4.4	4.2	4.4
Preferences	Color	5.7	5.9	6.3	6.4
	Smell	5.8	5.7	5.6	5.5
	Texture	5.7	5.6	5.4	5.4
	Taste	5.9	5.8	5.7	5.6
	general	6.1	6	5.9	5.6

The results for the preferences (evaluated with the 9 point scale) have been analyzed with the Friedman test since the population was not normal and that the samples were dependent. We set the hypothesis that H_0 : There is no difference between the four samples. For each subject, we ranked the grades from the preferences questions.

Here, n represents the number of participants and k the number of products. The value of the Friedman test can be obtained with the formula (6). Table 15 illustrates the Fr value of the 4 other preferences.

$$Fr = \frac{12}{n * k * (k + 1)} * \sum R^2 - 3 * n * (k + 1) \quad (6)$$

Table 13 : Results of the pratical value of Friedman for all our preferences criterias

	Preferences				
	Color	Smell	Texture	Taste	General appreciation
Fr	4.64	0.61	2.78	0.61	1.60

To understand the results, we have to compare our practical values with a theoretical critical value acquired from the statistics table (figure 7 in the annexes). With $k = 4$ and $n = 22$, the critical value read on the table with a risk of 5% is 7,80.

For all the attributes, the Friedman value calculated is under the critical value. This means that we keep the hypothesis H_0 and that there is no significant difference between the samples. So the results of the Friedman test are going in the same direction as the first test, that there is no significant difference between the blanching methods after a short storage.

b. Results of the just about right scale questions

The results of the second part of the preference tests which have been assessed on the just about right scale were harder to analyze with the Friedman test due to the scale particularity. We have chosen to represent them on a spider diagram (figure 15).

Figure 15 : Spider diagram of the characteristics of the mangoes blanched by four different methods, assessed by the preference test (in dark blue microwave HTST, in red microwave LTLT, in green water HTST, in purple water LTLT, in light blue the ideal sample)

The blue line represents that ideal sample which would have been graded as “just about right”. It matches with a grade of 5, for the 4 characteristics. We can see that all the blanched samples are located under this line. Figure 15 shows that the characteristics have to be more intense. All the samples are really close to each other. This fact confirms the results of all the previous tests, that there is no significant preference between the samples. However, we can see that the long time low temperature water blanched mango has higher grade for each of the characteristics.

No studies have been carried out about sensory comparison between microwave blanched and water blanched mangoes, however some have been for other fruits. According to the studies, microwave blanched samples are generally more firm than water boiled ones (Glasscock *et al.*, (1982); Lane *et al.*, (1984)) which is also what we got when we look at the spider diagram. There is no difference in the flavor between water, steam and microwave blanching for the green beans, yellow squash, purple hull peas and mustard greens (Lane *et al.*, 1984). Our results are not showing any significant differences either in the taste between the blanching methods. The preferences of the blanching methods seems to be related to the vegetable, however, Lana *et al.* found that boiled green peas were the less appreciated while Glasscock *et al.* found the opposite. In our case, there seem to be a tendency showing that water blanched samples are preferred.

IV. Conclusion

Fruits are hard matrices to work with because of their high natural variations (nutrients, maturity, brix value, water content). This has an influence of course on the experiments and their repeatability. To overcome this issue several repetitions are essential to evaluate the influence of the processing parameters.

The results from the blanching treatment seemed to be promising and in favor for the microwave blanching in terms of time. However the enzyme inactivation measurements are needed to make any conclusion.

The results of the sensory test couldn't show any significant difference between the samples on the short term storage. This analysis was a basic study made with the mean and time that we had, but it is essential information prior to further investigation. Indeed, if the products are appreciated the same by the consumers, it could be attractive for the industry to consider more sustainable processes such as microwave blanching.

Part of this work was presented at: E. Xanthakis, E. Kaunisto, M. Duvernay, A. Le-Bail, and L. Ahrné. Microwave Assisted Blanching and Novel Freezing Methods of Fruits. IUFoST-18th World Congress of Food Science and Technology. 21-25 August 2016, Dublin, Ireland

V. Bibliography

Scientific articles and books :

Boyes, S., Chevis, P., Holden, J., Perera, C. (1997). Microwave and water blanching of corn kernels: control of uniformity of heating during microwave blanching, *Journal of Food Processing and Preservation*, vol 21, 461-484.

Glasscock, S.J., Axelson, J.M., Palmer, J.K., Phillips, J.A., Taper, L.J. (1982). Microwave Blanching of Vegetables for frozen storage, *Home Economics Research Journal*, vol 11, n°2, 149-158.

Gonzalez, S.L., Lima, R.C.A., Carneiro, E.B.B., Mendes de Almeida, M., Rosse, N.D. (2011). Pectin methylesterase activity determined by different methods and thermal inactivation of exogenous PME in mango juice. *Ciência e Agrotecnologia*, vol 35, n°5, 987-994.

Guiamba, Isabelle. Nutritional value and quality of processed mango fruits. Phd thesis. Chalmers University of Technology, 2016, 80 p.

Jahurul, M.H., Zaidul, I.S., Ghafoor, K., Al-Juhaimi, F.Y., Nyam, K.L., Norulaini, N.A., Sahena, F., Mohd Omar, A.K. (2015). Mango (*Mangifera indica* L.) by-products and their valuable components: a review. *Food Chemistry*, vol 183, 173-180.

Lane ,R.H., Boschung, M.D., Abdel-ghany, M. (1984). Sensory comparison of prepared frozen vegetables processed by microwave and conventional methods of blanching, *Journal of Consumer Studies and Home Economics*, vol 8, 83-93.

Masibo, M., He, Q. (2009). Mango bioactive compounds and related nutraceutical properties. *Food Reviews International*, vol 25, 346-370.

Muftugil, N. Effect of different types of blanching on the color and the ascorbic acid and chlorophyll contents of green beans, *Journal of Food Processing and Preservation*, vol 10, 69-76.

Nadie, A., Zongo, A., Kabre, E., Nacro, S., Kabore, C., Ouedraogo, S., Guira, M. (2009). Manuel de formation participative sur la production de mangue biologique à travers les vergers-écoles au Burkina Faso. 69 p.

Patricia, C.M., Bibiana, D.Y., José, P.M. (2011). Evaluation of microwave technology in blanching of broccoli (*Brassica oleracea* L. var *Botrytis*) as a substitute for conventional blanching. *Procedia Food Science*, vol 1, 426-432.

Rahman, M.S. Handbook of Food Preservation, second edition. CRC press, 2007

Ramesh, M.N., Wolf, W., Tevini, D., Bognár, A. (2002). Microwave blanching of vegetables, *Journal of Food Science*, vol 67, n° 1, 390-398.

Rey, J-Y., Diallo, T.M., Vannière, H., Didier, C., Kéita, S., Morodja, S. (2007). The mango in French speaking West Africa: varieties and varietal composition of the orchards. *Fruits*, vol 62, n° 1, 57-73.

Xin, Y., Zhang, M., Xu, B., Adhikari, B., Sun, Jincui. (2015). Research trends in selected blanching pretreatments and quick freezing technologies as applied in fruits and vegetables: A review, *International Journal of Refrigeration*, vol 57, 11-25.

Vadivambal, R., Jayas, D.D. (2010). Non-uniform temperature distribution during microwave heating of food materials – A Review, *Food and Bioprocess Technology*, vol 3, 161-171.

Other ressources :

ECOWAS. Mangue Service des nouvelles des marchés. Bulletin MNS [Online]. 2011, 26 p. (consulted the 16th June 2016) Available at:

http://www.intracen.org/uploadedFiles/intracenorg/Content/About_ITC/Where_are_we_working/Multi-country_programmes/Pact_II/Mangoe%20report%20.pdf

Bargash, N. (2006). Cours transferts thermiques Convection [power point presentation].

(consulted the 8th October 2016) Available at : <http://www.fsr.ac.ma/cours/physique.html>

Paul Molin, Cours 1ère année de statistiques à AgroSup Dijon. (2015)

VI. Annexes

A. From the report

Date :					
Worksheet					
Type of test : triangular test 1 high temperature short time					
Samples identification :					
		Code		Three digit code	
Microwave blanched mangoes :		A		253 / 994	
Water blanched mangoes		B		547 / 165	
Order :					
Half of the participants should receive two microwaved mangoes and one water blanched and the other half should receive two water blanched and one microwaved.					
1	AAB	253 - 994 - 547	13	AAB	253 - 994 - 547
2	ABA	253 - 547 - 994	14	ABA	253 - 547 - 994
3	BAA	547 - 253 - 994	15	BAA	547 - 253 - 994
4	ABB	253 - 547 - 165	16	ABB	253 - 547 - 165
5	BAB	547 - 253 - 165	17	BAB	547 - 253 - 165
6	BBA	547 - 165 - 253	18	BBA	547 - 165 - 253
7	AAB	994 - 253 - 165	19	AAB	994 - 253 - 165
8	ABA	994 - 165 - 253	20	ABA	994 - 165 - 253
9	BAA	165 - 994 - 253	21	BAA	165 - 994 - 253
10	ABB	994 - 165 - 547	22	ABB	994 - 165 - 547
11	BAB	165 - 994 - 547	23	BAB	165 - 994 - 547
12	BBA	165 - 547 - 994	24	BBA	165 - 547 - 994

Figure 1 : Work sheet for the first triangle test

Figure 2 : Photo of the room of the sensory tests

TRIANGLE TESTS
<p>Taster number: Date : Gender :</p>
<p><u>Instructions :</u></p> <p>You are going to perform two triangle tests on mangos. For each test two samples are identical, one is different. Select the odd sample and indicate by placing an X next to the code of the odd sample.</p>
<p><u>TRIANGLE TEST 1</u></p> <p>Before testing, rinse your mouth with a sip of water. Taste the samples on the tray from left to right and mark the odd one. You have the possibility to try again the samples to confirm your choice.</p> <p style="text-align: center;"> _____ <input type="checkbox"/> _____ <input type="checkbox"/> _____ <input type="checkbox"/> </p>
<p><u>TRIANGLE TEST 2</u></p> <p>Before testing, rinse your mouth with a sip of water. Taste the samples on the tray from left to right and mark the odd one. You can try again the samples in the same order as before to confirm your choice.</p> <p style="text-align: center;"> _____ <input type="checkbox"/> _____ <input type="checkbox"/> _____ <input type="checkbox"/> </p>

Figure 3 : Questionnaires for the triangle test

PREFERENCE TEST
<p>Taster number: Gender :</p> <p>Do you like mangoes? : <input type="checkbox"/> yes <input type="checkbox"/> no</p> <p>How often do you eat mangoes? :</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> At least once a week <input type="checkbox"/> At least once a month <input type="checkbox"/> Once each 6 month <input type="checkbox"/> Once a year or less <input type="checkbox"/> never</p>
<p><u>Instructions :</u></p> <p>You are going to perform a consumer test on mangoes. You will receive 4 samples one after the other and have to answer the following questions.</p>

Figure 4: Introduction sheet for the preference test

SAMPLE :	
<i>Rinse your mouth before each sample. Do not eat it yet, you will first be asked some questions about the visual and physical characteristics.</i>	
<p style="text-align: center;"><u>How is the color?</u></p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Extremely light <input type="checkbox"/> slightly dark</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Very much light <input type="checkbox"/> moderately dark</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> moderately light <input type="checkbox"/> very much dark</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> slightly light <input type="checkbox"/> extremely dark</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> just about right</p>	<p style="text-align: center;"><u>How much did you like the color?</u></p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> like extremely <input type="checkbox"/> dislike slightly</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> like very much <input type="checkbox"/> dislike moderately</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> like moderately <input type="checkbox"/> dislike very much</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> like slightly <input type="checkbox"/> dislike extremely</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> neither like nor dislike</p>
<p style="text-align: center;"><u>What do you think about the smell?</u></p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Extremely weak <input type="checkbox"/> slightly intense</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Very much weak <input type="checkbox"/> moderately intense</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> moderately weak <input type="checkbox"/> very much intense</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> slightly weak <input type="checkbox"/> extremely intense</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> just about right</p>	<p style="text-align: center;"><u>How much did you like the smell?</u></p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> like extremely <input type="checkbox"/> dislike slightly</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> like very much <input type="checkbox"/> dislike moderately</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> like moderately <input type="checkbox"/> dislike very much</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> like slightly <input type="checkbox"/> dislike extremely</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> neither like nor dislike</p>
<i>Put a piece of the sample in your mouth and chew it a little bit to get an impression on the texture before swallowing.</i>	
<p style="text-align: center;"><u>How would you describe the texture?</u></p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Extremely soft <input type="checkbox"/> slightly tough</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Very much soft <input type="checkbox"/> moderately tough</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> moderately soft <input type="checkbox"/> very much tough</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> slightly soft <input type="checkbox"/> extremely tough</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> just about right</p>	<p style="text-align: center;"><u>How much did you like the texture?</u></p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> like extremely <input type="checkbox"/> dislike slightly</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> like very much <input type="checkbox"/> dislike moderately</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> like moderately <input type="checkbox"/> dislike very much</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> like slightly <input type="checkbox"/> dislike extremely</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> neither like nor dislike</p>
<p style="text-align: center;"><u>How is the sweet flavor?</u></p>	<p style="text-align: center;"><u>How much did you like the taste?</u></p>

<input type="checkbox"/> Extremely weak <input type="checkbox"/> Very much weak <input type="checkbox"/> moderately weak <input type="checkbox"/> slightly weak <input type="checkbox"/> just about right	<input type="checkbox"/> slightly strong <input type="checkbox"/> moderately strong <input type="checkbox"/> very much strong <input type="checkbox"/> extremely strong	<input type="checkbox"/> like extremely <input type="checkbox"/> like very much <input type="checkbox"/> like moderately <input type="checkbox"/> like slightly <input type="checkbox"/> neither like nor dislike	<input type="checkbox"/> dislike slightly <input type="checkbox"/> dislike moderately <input type="checkbox"/> dislike very much <input type="checkbox"/> dislike extremely
<p><u>General appreciation</u></p> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div style="text-align: left;"> <input type="checkbox"/> like extremely <input type="checkbox"/> like very much <input type="checkbox"/> like moderately <input type="checkbox"/> like slightly <input type="checkbox"/> neither like nor dislike </div> <div style="text-align: left;"> <input type="checkbox"/> dislike slightly <input type="checkbox"/> dislike moderately <input type="checkbox"/> dislike very much <input type="checkbox"/> dislike extremely </div> </div> <p>Comment :</p> <hr style="border: 0.5px solid black; margin-top: 10px;"/>			

Figure 5 : Questionnaires for the preference test

Nombre de réponses exprimées	Nb de réponses correctes nécessaire pour conclure à une différence significative. Seuils de confiance.		
	0,95	0,99	0,999
7	5	6	7
8	6	7	8
9	6	7	8
10	7	8	9
11	7	8	9
12	8	9	10
13	8	9	10
14	9	10	11
15	9	10	12
16	10	11	12
17	10	11	13
18	10	12	13
19	11	12	14
20	11	13	14
25	13	15	17
30	16	17	19
40	20	22	24
50	24	26	28
75	34	36	39
100	43	46	49

Figure 6: Critical number of correct answers for the triangle test

Figure 7 : Table of Friedman

K = 4	
n	Fr seuil
20	7.80
21	7.80
22	7.80
23	7.80
24	7.75

B.